

**New baseline and monitoring methodology proposal form
(Version 02.0)**

INFORMATION TO BE COMPLETED BY PROPONENTS

Name of the proponent: Cassio Luiz Vellani	
Affiliation:	<input type="checkbox"/> Designated National Authority (DNA) <input type="checkbox"/> Designated Operational Entity (DOE) <input type="checkbox"/> Project Participant (PP) <input type="checkbox"/> Coordinating / Managing Entity (CME) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other Stakeholder
Title of the proposed new methodology:	Greenhouse Gas Emissions Reduction through Vermicomposting of Organic Waste
Title of the proposed CDM project activity or programme of activities to be submitted for registration once methodology is approved:	NutriWash CDM – Emission Reductions through Vermicomposting of Organic Waste
Sectoral scope to which the proposed new methodology applies:	13 – Waste handling and disposal
Attachments:	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proposed new methodology (Please specify the form below) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> CDM-NM-FORM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CDM-SSC-NM-FORM <input type="checkbox"/> CDM-AR-NM-FORM <input type="checkbox"/> CDM-CCS-NM-FORM <input type="checkbox"/> Draft PDD or draft PoA-DD <input type="checkbox"/> Additional supporting information (Optional: please specify.....)	
Name of authorized officer signing for the proponent:	Cassio Luiz Vellani
Contact Information:	cassio.vellani@ifsp.edu.br
Date (DD/MM/YYYY) and signature for the proponent:	21 May 2025

Document information

<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Description</i>
01.0	21 May 2025	Initial publication. This document supersedes and replaces the following documents: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• CDM-PDD-FORM – Project Design Document• CDM-PNM-FORM – Proposal summary form• CDM-SSC-NM-FORM – Proposed small-scale methodology

Decision Class: Regulatory
Document Type: Form
Business Function: Methodology
Keywords: new methodology
